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Research Article

**A STUDY ON ALLERGIC RHINITIS (AR) AS A COMMON
ALLERGY DISORDER AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH
ASTHMA**¹Dr. Khaliq ur Rehman, ²Dr. Ayesha Shahjahan, ³Dr. Muhammad Ali Raza¹Polyclinic Hospital, Islamabad²Polyclinic Hospital³Quaid e Azam medical college Bahawalpur**Abstract:**

Introduction: Allergic rhinitis (AR) is a global health problem and one of the most common conditions seen by otolaryngologists. AR is characterised by one or more symptoms, including sneezing, itching, nasal congestion and rhinorrhea, and it may be classified by the temporal pattern of exposure to a triggering allergen (seasonal, perennial/year-round or episodic), frequency (intermittent or persistent) and severity of symptoms. **Objectives of the study:** The main goal of the study is to find the role of Allergic rhinitis (AR) as a common allergy disorder and its relationship with asthma. **Methodology:** This study was conducted at Polyclinic Hospital, Islamabad during 2017 to 2018. The data was collected from both genders. The sample size for this study was 50, ad those patients which was suffering from nose allergy and any other form of allergy was selected for this study. **Data collection:** Environmental and behavioral factors and medical history with a focus on allergies, including specific months when rhinitis symptoms without a cold occurred, were assessed at 9 time points by using face-to-face, paper, telephone, and online questionnaires. **Result:** Symptom scores were higher in the rhinitis than in control group during all of the experiments ($P < .001$) and were significantly elevated in both groups 4, 24, and 48 hours after beginning the challenge compared with baseline. Total cell count was significantly elevated in both groups. Table 1 summarizes the status of some SNPs associations with asthma in Pakistan and in some other populations as well as their allele frequency comparison with global MAF. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that allergy is generally caused by a sustained overproduction of IgE in response to common environmental antigens such as indoor and outdoor allergens, foods and other allergens and there is a need of more studies for the clarification of role of AR as a immunological disorder in Pakistan.

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INTRODUCTION:

Allergic rhinitis (AR) is a global health problem and one of the most common conditions seen by otolaryngologists. AR is characterised by one or more symptoms, including sneezing, itching, nasal congestion and rhinorrhea, and it may be classified by the temporal pattern of exposure to a triggering allergen (seasonal, perennial/year-round or episodic), frequency (intermittent or persistent) and severity of symptoms (mild or severe) [1]. The traditional classification system that divides AR into seasonal and perennial AR has limitations because the pollen season is dependent on geographic location and climatic conditions. When the pollen season is year-round, as in tropical locations, it is difficult to distinguish between symptoms provoked by pollens and mites [2]. In recent times, the incidence of allergic diseases, particularly bronchial asthma, has been increasing worldwide. Allergic rhinitis (AR) is the most common immunological disorder and is characterized by an immunoglobulin E (IgE)-mediated inflammation induced by allergen exposure. Infiltrating cells, including T cells, eosinophils, mast cells and basophils, release several mediators, that cause the symptoms occurrence, and cytokines, that promote and amplify the inflammatory cascade. Therefore, AR triggers both a local and a systemic inflammatory process [3]. The main symptoms are the so-called irritative ones, such as itching, sneezing and rhinorrhoea, that are histamine-dependent, and obstruction, that is inflammation-dependent [4].

AR is a risk factor for asthma. Two recent studies provided convincing confirmation that AR is an independent risk factor for asthma onset. It is reported that patients with AR are at three times the risk of developing asthma compared with those without AR. In addition, a cross-sectional study of representative samples of young adults, who completed a detailed questionnaire and underwent lung function tests, bronchoprovocation challenge, IgE measurement and skin prick test, has been performed in Europe [5].

Objectives of the study

The main goal of the study is to find the role of Allergic rhinitis (AR) as a common allergy disorder and its relationship with asthma

METHODOLOGY:

This study was conducted at Polyclinic Hospital. Islamabad during 2017 to 2018. The data was collected from both genders. The sample size for this study was 50, ad those patients which was suffering from nose allergy and any other form of allergy was selected for this study.

Data collection

Environmental and behavioral factors and medical history with a focus on allergies, including specific months when rhinitis symptoms without a cold occurred, were assessed at 9 time points by using face-to-face, paper, telephone, and online questionnaires. Specific IgE levels were measured at 9 time points. The study was approved by local institutional review boards in all study centers. Parents and participants provided written informed consent.

Statistical analysis

The influence of early-life exposures and behavior on AR was assessed by using time-to-event analysis. Disease onset was estimated at the midpoint between the first follow-up meeting case definition criteria and the prior negative (or missing) follow-up coded in days.

RESULTS:

Symptom scores were higher in the rhinitis than in control group during all of the experiments ($P < .001$) and were significantly elevated in both groups 4, 24, and 48 hours after beginning the challenge compared with baseline. Total cell count was significantly elevated in both groups. Table 1 summarizes the status of some SNPs associations with asthma in Pakistan and in some other populations as well as their allele frequency comparison with global MAF. Participants from both rich and poor backgrounds (grandparents and parents) had the same risk of AR as those from average-income families. Low parental education showed a weak association with lower AR incidence. Other aspects of the family's background were not linked to AR.

Table 01: Serum total IgE levels

Range (IU/L)	Mean (IU/L)	SD	Patients with raised total IgE	Patients with normal total IgE
25-860	285.01	±241.39	60 (57.14%)	45 (42.86%)

IgE: Immunoglobulin E.

Table 02: Analysis of relationship of AR and selected participants characteristics

Characteristic	OR (95% CI)	P Value
Symptom-based allergic rhinitis, KNHANES 2008-2012		
Male sex	1.04 (0.98-1.11)	.18
Aging	0.99 (0.98-0.99)	<.001
Urban residence	1.21 (1.06-1.38)	.005
Family income greater than average income	1.05 (0.98-1.13)	.19
Allergy test result-based allergic rhinitis,^a KNHANES 2010		
Male sex	1.19 (0.88-1.62)	.26
Aging	0.98 (0.97-0.99)	<.001
Urban residence	1.22 (0.85-1.75)	.27

DISCUSSION:

The prevalence of AR changes with genetics, epigenetics, and environmental exposure in complex ways not fully understood, and the prevalence has been cited as 10% to 30% of adults and up to 40% of children. Our results showed that the prevalence of AR was reported as 15%–25% by most of the participants, and it was stated to be “surely increasing” by 69.23% of the participants [6]. The opinions of participants regarding the reasons for the increasing prevalence of AR are “increased exposure to allergens, irritants and pollutants,” “change in lifestyle,” and “early exposure to allergens, irritants and pollutants.” It was reported that many causative agents have been linked to AR, including pollens, molds, dust mites, and animal dander. In many parts of the world, pollen allergy is very common; however, in Eastern Asia, Latin America, and tropical areas, mite allergy is more common [7].

AR is a multifactorial disease with genetic as well as environmental factors influencing disease development. Sensitisation to allergens may occur in early life [8,9]. Young maternal age, markers of fetal

growth, multiple gestation, mode of delivery, prematurity, low birth weight, growth retardation, hormones during pregnancy, and perinatal asphyxia were all inconstantly related to the risk of developing allergic diseases or rhinitis. Challenges with non-allergenic stimuli on target organs of allergic diseases (eg, the nose, lung, eye, and skin) have shown that the degree of nonspecific tissue reactivity contributes significantly to the clinical picture of allergic diseases, and the heterogeneity of allergic phenotypes is best approached taking into account a wider variety of symptom triggers [10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that allergy is generally caused by a sustained overproduction of IgE in response to common environmental antigens such as indoor and outdoor allergens, foods and other allergens and there is a need of more studies for the clarification of role of AR as a immunological disorder in Pakistan. IgE-mediated nasal response but have some features in common.

REFERENCES:

1. Van Beijsterveldt CE, Boomsma DI. Genetics of parentally reported asthma, eczema and rhinitis in 5-yr-old twins. *Eur Respir J* 2007;29:516-21.
2. Kulig M, Bergmann R, Tacke U, Wahn U, Guggenmoos-Holzmann I. Long-lasting sensitization to food during the first two years precedes allergic airway disease. The MAS Study Group, Germany. *Pediatr Allergy Immunol* 1998;9:61-7.
3. Hatzler L, Panetta V, Lau S, Wagner P, Bergmann RL, Illi S, et al. Molecular spreading and predictive value of preclinical IgE response to *Phleum pratense* in children with hay fever. *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2012;130:894-901.e5.
4. Westman M, Stjarne P, Asarnej A, Kull I, van Hage M, Wickman M, et al. Natural course and comorbidities of allergic and nonallergic rhinitis in children. *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2012;129:403-8.
5. Higgins TS, Reh DD. Environmental pollutants and allergic rhinitis. *Curr Opin Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg* 2012;20:209-14.
6. Codispoti CD, Levin L, LeMasters GK, Ryan P, Reponen T, Villareal M, et al. Breast-feeding, aeroallergen sensitization, and environmental exposures during infancy are determinants of childhood allergic rhinitis. *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2010;125:1054-60.e1.
7. Tariq SM, Matthews SM, Hakim EA, Arshad SH. Egg allergy in infancy predicts respiratory allergic disease by 4 years of age. *Pediatr Allergy Immunol* 2000;11: 162-7.
8. Kellberger J, Dressel H, Vogelberg C, Leupold W, Windstetter D, Weinmayr G, et al. Prediction of the incidence and persistence of allergic rhinitis in adolescence: a prospective cohort study. *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2012;129:397-402, e1-3.
9. Bousquet J, Schunemann HJ, Samolinski B, Demoly P, Baena-Cagnani CE, Bachert C, et al. Allergic Rhinitis and its Impact on Asthma (ARIA): achievements in 10 years and future needs. *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2012;130:1049-62.
10. Grabenhenrich LB, Gough H, Reich A, Eckers N, Zepp F, Nitsche O, et al. Earlylife determinants of asthma from birth to age 20 years: a German birth cohort study. *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2014;133:979-88.
11. Graf N, Johansen P, Schindler C, Wuthrich B, Ackermann-Liebrich U, Gassner M, et al. Analysis of the relationship between pollinosis and date of birth in Switzerland. *Int Arch Allergy Immunol* 2007;143:269-75.